

Cultural Challenges and Pedagogical Adaptation: A Mixed-Methods Study of ESL Learning in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa

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Abstract

This study examines how cultural factors influence the learning of English as a Second Language (ESL) in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Pakistan. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from over 100 students and 20 teachers through structured questionnaires featuring both closed- and open-ended questions. Drawing on Sociocultural Theory, Acculturation Theory, and Ecological Systems Theory, the study explores how family dynamics, peer attitudes, community norms, and educational environments shape ESL learning outcomes. The findings reveal a complex interaction between cultural identity and language acquisition: while many families and teachers support ESL education, cultural expectations, limited rural infrastructure, and social stigma create barriers that hinder progress. Additionally, both students and teachers adapt to cultural differences in the learning process, with teachers incorporating culturally relevant materials and students often modifying their behaviors to align with English language norms. The study concludes that ESL learning in KPK cannot be fully understood without accounting for its cultural context and emphasizes the need for culturally responsive teaching strategies that support learners' linguistic and cultural identities.

Keywords: *ESL Learning, Cultural Factors, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK), Sociocultural Theory, Acculturation, Ecological Systems Theory, Language and Identity, Culturally Responsive Pedagogy, Urban-Rural Divide, English Language Education in Pakistan*

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1. Introduction

In contemporary times, as the world has become a global village, multilingualism has emerged as an essential means for individuals to assimilate into other cultures. Within this global landscape of linguistic diversity, acquiring English as a Second Language (ESL) is considered a vital skill. Culture, often defined as a way of life, plays a significant role in many aspects of people's lives. While language and culture may appear distinct, they mutually influence one another. Language both shapes and is shaped by society, suggesting that it is not an isolated entity but a form of social practice (Kuo & Lai, 2006). The current study investigates the influence of cultural elements in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa (KPK) on the learning of English as a Second language. It explores both the facilitators and barriers that cultural factors present to ESL learning.

Multilingualism in Pakistan has been a common practice from the outset, with people learning both Urdu and English. English, as a global lingua franca, is often perceived more as a symbol of success and a gateway to opportunities than merely a medium of communication. This mindset drives the emphasis on English language learning and embeds the language into nearly every community in some form. However, the widespread learning of English brings it into contact with the diverse cultural landscape of Pakistan and also leaves it susceptible to the influence of regional sociocultural factors and is particularly evident in Khyber Pakhtunkhwa.

KPK, with its rich linguistic and cultural heritage, offers a distinctive sociocultural setting for language acquisition. Language learning extends beyond the mechanics of grammar and vocabulary. It is deeply influenced by cultural norms, values, and practices. The region's diverse cultural traditions shape both the opportunities and challenges associated with learning English as a Second Language. In KPK, English is often perceived as a key to social and economic advancement, which makes the interaction between cultural factors and ESL learning particularly significant. Understanding this intersection provides valuable insights into how cultural dynamics impact language education in the region.

This research draws upon theoretical foundations from Sociocultural Theory, Acculturation Theory, and Ecological Systems Theory to develop a comprehensive conceptual framework. The study

emphasizes that cultural dimensions such as social interactions, traditional values, and peer attitudes play a significant role in shaping ESL learning experiences in KPK. By exploring these factors, the research aims to provide a nuanced understanding of how the cultural context affects language acquisition in the region.

Problem Statement

The growing global importance of English as a lingua franca has led to a significant increase in the number of ESL learners in the culturally diverse region of KPK, Pakistan. This rise is further driven by increasing immigration for employment, education, and tourism. However, despite this surge, there remains a lack of focused research on how the distinct cultural factors of KPK influence ESL learning. Cultural norms, values, and practices play a crucial role in shaping language acquisition, yet their specific impact within the context of KPK remains underexplored. This study aims to identify and analyze the cultural factors unique to KPK that affect ESL learners, thereby addressing a critical gap in the current understanding of language education in this region.

Research Objectives

The primary objective of this study is to examine how cultural factors specific to KPK influence the process of learning English as a Second Language.

Research Questions

This study seeks to address the following research questions:

1. What specific cultural barriers hinder ESL learning in the context of KPK?
2. In what ways do cultural factors influence ESL learning outcomes in KPK?

2. Literature Review

The exploration of cultural factors on ESL learning in KPK finds resonance in existing literature, drawing insights from the likes of Serajuddin's work on a similar topic in Bangladesh. This study provides a foundational understanding of the relationship between cultural factors and ESL learning. The study also talks about the significance of understanding the native cultural background, which will ultimately help in a better learning experience for the students of ESL (Serajuddin, 2023).

Thus, due to the importance of ESL, parents tend to provide their children with the best environment for ESL learning, and therefore parents send their kids to private rather than public institutes (Sharmin, 2019). Similarly, in KPK, most parents tend to provide their children with a suitable environment for learning ESL. Ara notes that cultural elements also have a huge role to play in ESL classrooms (Ara, 2020).

Serajuddin further digs deep, unraveling the relationship between culture and language. Serajuddin recognizes language learning as an intertwined effort with culture. ESL learning also stems from the colonial roots of the region. Taking this research as a foundational study for the chosen topic provides valuable depth into the impacts of cultural factors on ESL learning (Serajuddin, 2023).

Another work by Kuo and Lai, titled “Linguistics across Cultures: The Impact of Culture on Second Language Learning,” provides information on the relationship between culture and language. The work underlines the inseparable relationship of culture and language. Their work stresses the role of cultural understanding for linguistic comprehension. The study emphasizes the integration of culture as an essential element of teaching and learning any second language. It also suggests that paying more attention to cultural diversity helps to bridge the cultural gap effectively (Kuo & Lai, 2006). The amalgamation of culture and language as essential elements of each other provides a strong foundation, especially considering the diverse cultures of ESL students in KPK. The teaching of ESL, along with the cultural context of the language, can be vital to improved learning.

Culture, defined as a way of life (Condon, 1973), includes the ideas, customs, skills, and beliefs of people in a given area and time. Thus, culture is linked to different aspects of everyday life. Language, as well, cannot exist in a ‘vacuum’ and thus there is a “transfusion” between culture and language (Fairclough, 2001). Language is a product as well as a symbol of culture, wherein social customs are encoded in language (Gleason, 1961). This is reinforced by Armour-Thomas and Gopaul-McNicol, saying that language is not an independent entity but is undeniably linked to social institutions. Thus, language has to be studied in association with the culture, and language learning will always include cultural learning (Armour-Thomas & Gopaul-McNicol, 1998). This reiterates the need to teach ESL in the classroom while providing students with the associated cultural practices of the second language, as well as keeping in view their existing cultural background. Second language learning can also be seen as learning a new culture since a learner can never master a language unless

they have command over the cultural context of the language (Lu, 1998). Thus, learning ESL comes bundled with learning the culture of the language.

According to Lado, if certain features of a second language differ greatly from the native language of a learner, then the learner is likely to face problems in learning (Lado & Walsh, 1957). Therefore, teachers must plan according to the culture of the students, leading to an improved learning experience. The ambiguities faced by learners of a second language can be addressed, and the learning curve of a new language can be greatly reduced by exposing learners to the culture where the language takes place (Aljumah, 2020). According to Kramersch, for achieving true linguistic comprehension, culture and language should be learned together (Kramersch, 1998). This restates the need to integrate the teaching of cultural contexts parallel to second language learning and teaching.

Zoltán Kövecses discusses the connection between language and culture in a multitude of ways. According to his study, the use of proverbs, politeness, metaphor, semantic change, discourse, and so forth, is just some of the areas showing connections between culture and language (Kövecses, 2010). For Abdulrahman, foreign language learning has become a significant component of the global education system, and cultural factors are known to have an impact on the process of language learning (Abdulrahman, 2023). Mohammed calls language and culture “two sides of the same coin” in his work. According to him, cultural factors cannot be ignored while learning a second language, as they provide a broader understanding. Mohammed points to the notion of neglecting cultural knowledge, leading to limited knowledge of a language (AbdAlgane Mohammed, 2020). This study further reemphasizes the idea that culture and language are linked phenomena, and both are important to comprehend in order to have complete command over a language.

Pakistan is an underdeveloped country (Ahmar, 2011), and due to the colonial legacy, the English language is seen as a highway to opportunities. The study by Nisar et al. systematically digs into the challenges faced by ESL learners in Pakistan and searches to find the role of socio-cultural norms and their impact on ESL classroom practices. The study further notes the lack of training provided to the teachers on encompassing socio-cultural norms in ESL teaching. The research underlines the importance of complete culturally inclusive practices within the ESL classroom (Nisar et al., 2023). The work of Nisar et al. points to flaws in the educational system, as a lack of proper teacher training and planning hinders learning language and the cultural context.

Many researchers have established that culture can cause a delay in learning a second language. For Amin, the major cultural fences are social influences. This work investigates factors that can hinder the learning of language. Culture is an integral part of every human's life. Thus, there are challenges in learning a language in different contexts. Cultural difference creates a psychological distance for the second language learner, which hinders the learning of a new language. Understanding the culture and traditions helps greatly in the solution of ESL learners' problems (Amin, 2015). Thus, a lack of proper understanding of the cultural contexts of ESL students creates a psychological distance in the minds of the ESL learners.

Aqeel et al. define language as a basic aspect of human identity, transmitting communication between the self and the world. Human identity has many influencing factors, including language and culture. English holds the crown spot in most former British colonies, including Pakistan. The study mainly identifies the role of sociocultural factors in the learning of ESL. This idea is that language and culture are linked and have a constant impact on each other (Aqeel et al., 2023).

Taking into consideration the insights from the literature, a considerable foundation emerges for further exploration into the topic. The works stress the interrelation of culture and language learning, helping the study in understanding the cultural dimensions influencing ESL in KPK. The people of KPK consider the English language as an indicator of future success. Since language and culture are mutually influential, the culture of KPK will certainly leave its mark on English as a second language.

3. Research Methodology

3.1. Research Design

The study employs a mixed-method approach including both qualitative and quantitative data for analysis. This method answers both through quantitative and qualitative methods (Shorten & Smith, 2017). The data collection method includes the use of Questionnaires tailored for students and teachers. The data collected is primary data for the identification of the impact of socio-cultural factors on ESL learners and to determine the challenges faced by teachers of ESL created by socio-cultural factors.

3.2. Data Collection

The data is collected through questionnaire forms for learners and teachers of ESL. A well-structured questionnaire is developed, consisting of both closed-ended and open-ended questions, keeping in view the research objectives. Open-ended questions serve as qualitative data, whereas closed-ended questions provide quantitative data. The data contains responses from more than a hundred students of KPK. About 20 ESL teachers from all over KPK responded to the questionnaire with their views.

3.3. Conceptual Framework

The study utilizes some aspects of multiple frameworks to analyze the collected data.

3.3.1. Sociocultural Theory.

The sociocultural theory presented by Vygotsky provides an understanding of the topic. The conceptual framework mainly posits that language learning is a social practice, shaped by cultural norms (Vygotsky, 1978). The concept of culturally-relevant teaching is central to the study. Culturally-Relevant Teaching refers to the incorporation of references to help the students in their learning.

3.3.2. Acculturation Theory.

The acculturation theory of second language acquisition by John Schumann provides a theoretical background for this study. The theory mainly examines the adjustments of an individual to a new environment (Schumann, 1986). The acculturation theory presents concepts like the Acculturation Strategies, including Assimilation, Separation, Integration, and Marginalization. Assimilation is the adoption of a new culture while abandoning the original culture. Separation is the retention of the old culture while rejecting the new one. Integration is the upkeep of both old and new cultures, whereas Marginalization is the loss of connections to both old and new cultures.

3.3.3. Ecological Systems Theory.

The Ecological Systems Theory was offered by Urie Bronfenbrenner, emphasizing the inter-relationship of individuals with their socio-cultural environment. The theory provides concepts for the conceptual framework, including Microsystem, Mesosystem, Exosystem, Macrosystem, and

Chronosystem. A microsystem is an individual's direct interactions, containing their family, peers, and teachers. Mesosystem is a larger web of microsystems, for example, the different contexts that a person regularly visits. Exosystem is the broader social system that affects a person's development. The Macrosystem comprises the cultural norms influencing a person, whereas a chronosystem contains the changes in a person's life.

4. Analysis

The study employed the use of a mixed-method design where both qualitative and quantitative data were collected from students and teachers to get a multi-dimensional perspective on the topic. The responses were collected from over a hundred students and over twenty teachers of English in KPK for analysis in the current research.

4.1. Demographic Data

The questionnaire required both students and teachers. The majority of the students were between the ages of 19 to 26. An overwhelming number of students (72%) were female, whereas 28% were male. A majority of the students were from the undergraduate level (64%), while about 29% of the students were at the postgraduate level. Learners who had been learning English for more than 10 years formed more than 60% of the total demography, and more than 90% of the responders had Urdu and Pashto as their native language.

Regarding the teachers, half of the respondents had been teaching English for more than 10 years, 20% had been teaching English for 7-10 years, whereas the rest had experience of 1-3 years in teaching English. 30% of the teachers were teaching at the high school level, whereas 20% were ESL teachers from undergraduate or postgraduate levels.

4.2. Quantitative Data Findings

The quantitative data were collected from the responses of both students and teachers to closed-ended questions in the questionnaire.

4.2.1. Students' Perspective on Cultural Influence on ESL.

The student questionnaire consisted of closed-ended questions, which formed the quantitative data. The questionnaire was divided into different sections for ease of data analysis.

4.2.1.A Family and Community Influence.

The first section was regarding family influence and the community of ESL students. Family and community form the first layer of exposure, and they introduce and reinforce cultural norms. The closed-ended questions that formed the questionnaire were:

The recorded responses to the questions are as follows:

S. No.	Closed-Ended Questions	Very supportive	Somewhat supportive	Neutral	Not very supportive	Not very supportive at all
1	How supportive is your family in your English learning efforts?	62.8%	10.9%	20.9%	3.1%	2.3%
2	How supportive is your community towards learning and using English?	19.4%	45.7%	22.5%	9.3%	3.1%
S. No.	Closed-Ended Questions	Very positively	positively	Neutral	Negatively	Very Negatively
3	How do you think your cultural norms and values affect or influence your attitude and motivation towards learning English?	17.8%	32.6%	36.4%	10.1%	3.1%
S. No	Closed-Ended Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
4	Do your cultural factors and beliefs hinder your learning of English?	10.2%	32%	25.8%	21.9%	9.4%

Table 1: Family and Community Influence on Students

The first question was regarding family support in ESL learning, as family forms the first source of cultural information. The responses had a positive trend where the majority of families showed a “Very Supportive” attitude towards students’ ESL activities. About 11% of parents and family members showed “somewhat support,” whereas about 21% of the students’ families showed neutrality on the students’ ESL activities. Some responses also showed non-supportive behavior. Since the family system is a part of the KPK culture, it is important for the family to be supportive in most cases, as the family is the primary source of support.

The second closed-ended question was regarding the support of the community towards the learning activity. The students’ responses mostly suggested that the community was “somewhat supportive” of the learning and use of the English language.

Another question was regarding whether or not the cultural norms of a person affect their attitude towards learning ESL. The majority of the responses suggested that the cultural norms have no or a somewhat positive influence on their attitude towards ESL. Family and community play an important role in a person’s life, and their positive response toward ESL learning shows a positive trend towards embracing foreign languages.

The final question was related to the influence of cultural factors and beliefs on the learning of ESL. In responses, the majority of the students “agreed” that their cultural factors hindered their ESL learning. On the contrary, the students who showed disagreement with the statement suggested that their cultural beliefs present no hindrance towards their learning of English, which was also quite high (~22%), and about 26% of the students said that their cultural beliefs and factors were neutral to their learning.

These students’ responses show the importance of social interaction according to the sociocultural theory. The support of family and peers is vital to the formation of a positive learning environment. According to the Ecological System theory, this lies in the Microsystem, whereby students of ESL are in interaction with their family and are being influenced by their broader cultural context.

4.2.1.B Cultural Relevancy and Adaptation.

Another section of questions in the questionnaire was concerned with the barriers that culture or language learning presents and the adaptations that the learner has to make in order to learn ESL. The questions that were asked in this category were:

S. No	Closed-Ended Question	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	I have to modify my cultural behaviors in order to learn English.	7.8%	33.6%	29.7%	25%	3.9%
S. No	Closed-Ended Question	Very relevant	Relevant	Neutral	Irrelevant	Very Irrelevant
2	Do you find the English learning materials culturally relevant and relatable?	6.2%	38.8%	38%	14%	3.1%
S. No	Closed-Ended Question	Very effective	Effective	Neutral	Ineffective	Very ineffective
3	How effective do you find the current teaching methods used for English in your educational institution?	12.4%	34.1%	29.5%	17.1%	7%

Table 2: Cultural Relevance and Adaptation

The first question asked the students if they had to modify their cultural norms and behaviors in order to learn ESL. A majority (33.6%) of the students responded in agreement to the statement showing an interlink between culture and language learning, especially in KPK. About 30% of students also showed neutrality towards the idea, and 25% of the students disagreed with any modification in their cultural behavior to learn English.

Another question under this category was related to the cultural relevance of the learning material for English to the native culture of the student or the culture of KPK. Around 39% of the total student respondents found the learning material culturally relevant.

Another question regarding the effectiveness of the teaching methods used for ESL learning in the educational institutions of KPK was Similar to the cultural relevance of the material used to teach English, where the majority of students found the teaching methods used for teaching ESL in their educational institutions effective.

The questions and responses show signs of culturally-relevant teaching, according to sociocultural theory, where cultural backgrounds are incorporated into teaching ESL. The responses are also relevant to the Acculturation theory's "Integration," where students retain both the old and new cultures. The main context of macrosystem is also present, whereby students of ESL are in a system with their cultural norms.

4.2.1.C Environmental and Societal Factors.

Social factors also contribute to influencing ESL learning in KPK. Students were asked questions regarding the social factors that may be affecting their progress towards learning ESL. These questions were asked to understand the interconnectivity of ESL to societal changes. The following questions were asked in the questionnaire:

S.no.	Closed-Ended Questions	Strongly Agree	Agree	Neutral	Disagree	Strongly disagree
1	Is there a good learning environment for learning English as a Second Language in the Urban areas of KPK?	10.1%	45%	24.8%	13.2%	7%
2	Is there a good learning environment for learning English as a Second Language in the rural areas of KPK?	6.2%	19.4%	19.4%	41.1%	14%

Table 3 Environmental and Societal Factors

The first question was about the learning environment in the urban areas of KPK. The students' responses showed agreement on the presence of an appropriate learning environment for learning ESL in the urban areas of KPK.

The second question was regarding the environment for learning ESL in the rural areas of KPK. According to the data, students showed an overwhelming disagreement with the presence of a good learning environment for ESL in rural areas of KPK.

The questions and the responses suggest a link between the environment and learning ESL. It also points towards the presence of an influence of culture on the learning of ESL in KPK.

4.2.2. Teachers' Perspective on Cultural Influence on ESL.

The questionnaire for English teachers in KPK consisted of both open-ended and closed-ended questions. Closed-ended questions were asked to receive quantitative data. The responses by teachers helped in understanding the influence of cultural factors on ESL learning from their perspective.

4.2.2.A Family Influence.

One of the main factors in the learning of ESL is the influence of family on the students' learning. Family support can motivate students to learn ESL effectively and vice versa. The question asked regarding family influence was:

Question	Very supportive	Supportive	Neutral	Unsupportive	Very unsupportive
How supportive are the parents of your students in their English learning?	15%	60%	5%	15%	5%

Table 4: Family Influence

The responses of teachers included about 75% of teachers thinking that the parents of students have a supportive attitude towards their ESL learning. About 20% of the teacher responses suggested unsupportive attitudes of parents towards learning ESL.

The responses show the importance of social interaction between family members according to sociocultural theory. The positive influence of family members goes a long way in motivating the learner of ESL. The context provided was the mesosystem where the interaction of the learner and their parents is the main focus of the discussion.

4.2.2.B Cultural Relevancy and Adaptation.

Teaching culturally-relevant material to students helps their progress in learning ESL and also helps the learners to have contextual learning that they can relate to during the learning of the language. This section of questions was designed to get the teachers' perspective on the use of culturally-relevant material during teaching. The questions were:

S.no.	Questions	Very Relevant	Relevant	Neutral	Irrelevant	Very irrelevant
1	How culturally relevant are the English learning materials you use?	10%	80%	10%	0%	0%
S.no.	Questions	Always	Often	Sometimes	Rarely	Never
2	Do you adapt your teaching materials to better suit the cultural backgrounds of your students?	10%	75%	15%	0%	0%

Table 5 Cultural Relevance and Adaptation

The first question was designed to inquire if teachers used material to teach English that was relevant to the context. An overwhelming majority (90%) of teachers affirmed culturally-relevant teaching. This suggests the interplay between culture and language, whereby culture can influence the learning of ESL.

A subsequent question regarding teaching material was also asked to see if they adapted their teaching material to suit the cultural background of the students. The recorded data suggests a predominant adaptation of teaching material to the cultural backgrounds of the students.

The notion of the acculturation strategy known as integration applies to this setting. The teachers here try to hold on to their own culture, while also presenting and teaching a new culture that they also cannot let go of.

4.2.2.C Environmental and Cultural Factors

The cultural context of a student has a profound impact on their learning of ESL. The teachers were asked whether they think the students are affected by their surrounding factors.

S.no.	Questions	Positively	Negatively	Neutral	It varies
1	How do cultural factors affect student engagement in English language classes?	0%	15%	70%	15%

Table 6: Environmental and Cultural Factors

The teachers' response suggests a mixed effect of cultural factors on student engagement in ESL classrooms. The teachers' responses also suggest that cultural factors do not affect student engagement in a positive manner in any case.

The context of the macrosystem is very appropriate to this context, as the teachers are responding to questions that study the effects of cultural factors on the learner of ESL.

4.3. Qualitative Data Findings

The qualitative data is collected from responses to open-ended questions included in the questionnaire.

4.3.1. Students' Perspective on Cultural Influence on ESL Learning.

The questionnaire for students consisted of open-ended questions to communicate the students' views on the current study. The open-ended questions were also categorized for ease of analysis of the data.

4.3.1.A Cultural Influence on ESL Learning.

Qualitative questions were asked concerning the influence of culture on the journey of ESL learning. The following question was asked:

Open-Ended Question	Do you think your cultural background has influenced your English learning journey? If yes, kindly elaborate on your experience.
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Student's Response Prototype
<p>“Yes, it affects my journey. As everyone is not fond of speaking English language and they feel it difficult while speaking so they prefer their native language over English.”</p>

Table 7 Cultural Influence on ESL Learning

The question was tailored to allow ESL students to provide their perspective on the interplay between culture and their learning. A consuming majority of students consider their culture as a hindrance in their journey towards learning ESL. One student responded by saying that their culture made them more hesitant to speak English due to the fear of making mistakes. Some respondents called their “small village” context a hindrance. A few of the responses were also in disagreement with the hindrance, as one student responded, “Well, we have been taught English through private schools, so I guess yeah it did help us.”

These responses show an overwhelming favor for the influence of cultural background on ESL learning. These responses point towards the presence of the influence of cultural factors of KPK students on their ESL learning.

The concepts of acculturation strategies apply here, whereby many students want to integrate a new culture with their existing culture. Other students, however, show Separation whereby they retain their old culture and reject the new culture that they are being exposed to. The wider context of the chronosystem applies here, as most of the students’ responses contain a shift in their lives with time. The ecological system of macrosystem equally applies here, as there is an influence of cultural norms on the students.

4.3.1.B Impact of ESL Learning on Culture.

The possibility of learning a language impacting the cultural norms of the learners was also investigated with the help of questions. The questions asked of students under this category were:

Q. No	Open-Ended Questions	
1	Do you feel that learning English affects your cultural identity? If yes, how?	
Students Responses Prototypes		
	“Absolutely, culture is indeed dynamic. It's not static or fixed, but evolves over time through interactions, and adaptations within societies and between different cultures.”	“No, it doesn't change one cultural identity but being an international language, it helps in better understanding one's own culture through other cultures.”
2	Do you feel that the reading and learning material in English classrooms is against cultural norms? If yes, how? Also, specify the material that makes you feel this way.	
Students Responses Prototypes		
	“Yes, I saw a book in which a foreign girl without shawl, open hair and short skirt was defined as defined and a girl wearing cultural dress covering herself was pointed out as ugly.”	“No, not inherently. However, some reading and learning materials in English classrooms may reflect cultural norms and values specific to English-speaking countries, which can differ from those of other cultures.”
3	Do you think the teacher promotes foreign cultural content in the class? If yes, then how?	
Students Responses Prototypes		
	“Yes, because a teacher introduces foreign culture curriculum like history and literature.”	“No, they teach us everything in our own context”

Table 8: Impact of ESL Learning on Culture

The first question was asked to explore any impact on the cultural identity of a learner. The overall response was mixed, and a lot of responders considered learning ESL just as a language for better employment opportunities and to understand the “mass of information available in English.”

One student responded by stating, “In our culture, there are so many things that are affected by learning English, such as Identity. Our goals, ideas, and psychology have been altered, and now we have a hybrid identity.” Many students declared the influence of English as having a positive impact on their lives by “opening doors to new cultural experiences,” facilitating “access to knowledge and expression of heritage.”

The second question also received mixed responses. Some students declined reading and learning material as being against cultural norms, saying, “The learning material is very much in line with the cultural norms.” Other learners suggested that “implementing English as a language is good, adopting it as culture is bad”, yet others stated that “Some English classroom materials may be perceived as conflicting with cultural norms due to stereotypes, or Western values.”

The question of the promotion of foreign culture by teachers also saw a divided opinion. Some suggested that teachers do not promote foreign cultural content in ESL classes at all, saying, “No, they teach us everything in our context.” Other students affirmed this view by saying that the teachers use foreign cultural elements in the classroom as a “backdrop or context of the culture so that it helps in the language learning.”

4.3.2. Teachers’ Perspective on Cultural Influence on ESL Learning.

Teachers’ perspectives on the interplay between cultural factors and ESL learning in KPK were collected through their responses to open-ended questions. The questions were designed in a thematic sequence to assist in ease of understanding and analysis.

4.3.2.A Cultural Influence on Students’ ESL Learning.

Teachers were asked questions regarding their perspective on the influence of cultural factors that can affect ESL learners in any way. Some of the questions under this category were:

Q.no.	Questions
1	What cultural challenges do you observe students facing in learning English?
Teacher Responses	
“Their accent and pronunciation act as barriers in English learning.”	“Culture of not speaking English at home is the biggest hurdle”

2	What cultural strengths do you observe that help students learn English?	
Teacher Response		
Cultural strengths, such as diverse perspectives and multilingual abilities, enhance their adaptability and understanding of English.		
3	How do you incorporate students’ cultural backgrounds into your teaching methods?	
Teacher Responses		
Use of textbooks, multimedia, and resources that represent a variety of cultures and languages		By using culturally-relevant examples, stories, and materials in my teaching methods.

Table 9: Cultural Influence on Students’ ESL Learning

The question of cultural challenges that students face from the teacher’s perspective received a multitude of responses. Many teachers pointed towards the common factor of being “more focused on local languages” rather than focusing on ESL. Other teachers also gave a similar response, where one of the teachers cited a “culture of not speaking English at home” as a hurdle, and another teacher stated that students are “not used to the English language” in a way that is “similar to their mother tongue.” Other teachers indicated other factors, such as “Difficult vocabulary” and “not strong basics” as cultural challenges that students of ESL face. Another environmental factor given by one of the teachers was “being laughed at by peers,” leading to a loss of motivation, whereas another teacher stated that the students “find it hard to understand cultural references,” which acts as a hurdle in effective learning of the English language.

The teachers also acknowledged some cultural strengths that help the students improve their ESL learning. The teacher responses mentioned factors such as “Positive family impact”, students’ “desire to learn” from surroundings, and being “open to learning about cultures” as strengths that help students in ESL learning.

The teachers talked about using “multimedia” and other resources to incorporate students’ cultural backgrounds in their teaching. Many teachers alluded to sharing “personal experiences” and

“culturally-relevant examples” as strategies to help incorporate the cultural backgrounds of students into their teaching.

4.3.2.B Impact of ESL Learning on Culture.

Language and culture have a dynamic interplay. Similar to the questions asked of students, the impact of learning ESL on culture was also investigated through questions.

Question	
Does learning English impact your students' cultural identity, from your perspective? If so, how?	
Teacher Responses Prototypes	
“Learning English can influence students' cultural identity by expanding their worldviews and facilitating communication across cultures.”	“To some extent, as they learn about English culture and may adapt it in their lives after reading about it repetitively”

Table 10: Impact of ESL Learning on Culture

The teachers mostly responded positively. Some teachers thought that English learning does have an impact “to some extent,” while others responded that it often “leads to a blend of traditional and modern values.” Other teachers talked about the interconnected nature of culture and language by saying, “If someone wants to learn a language, that individual has to understand the culture and put him or herself in that culture.”

These responses to questions were centered around the notion that culture and language have an intertwined relationship and a dynamic relationship, both influencing each other.

4.4. Discussion

The responses to questions by students and teachers show the profound influence of the culture of KPK on the learning of ESL, as well as the impact of ESL learning on the cultural contexts of KPK. The data suggests that culture and language are interconnected ideas that influence each other in KPK. The responses also imply that the persistent influence of cultural background, context, and familial reaction contributes to either affecting the learning of ESL in KPK. The impact of landscape from

urban to rural also has a significant impact on the learning environment, which, coupled with factors such as family resistance, furthers the impact of culture on the learning of ESL.

The combined effect of the three theories – The Sociocultural Theory, Acculturation Theory, and Ecological Systems Theory - also helps in giving a different perspective on the responses, as well as provides insight into the importance and relevance of the results of each category of questions.

One of the major findings of this research is that a lot of learners do not feel supported in the broader cultural context. Many students feel that family and societal attitude influence their learning. Students also pointed out that in their context, most of their friends prefer speaking in the local language, which limits their learning progress. Many students also felt the need to modify their cultural behaviors to learn ESL. Another finding of the difference in learning environment for ESL between urban and rural areas presents itself as a major cause for concern in KPK.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, the study explores the cultural factors that influence the learning of ESL in KPK. Subsequent to the examination of the data, the research found that language learning is indeed influenced by the cultural factors of KPK. Some of the cultural factors improve the learning while other factors hinder the learning of English. The research also found that ESL learning influences the cultural cognition of learners. On the other hand, ESL teachers also have to adapt their teaching to the needs of the learners, relevant to the learners' cultural background. Thus, cultural factors influence the learning of ESL in KPK.

5.1. Recommendations

Based on the analysis findings from the data, there are certain recommendations to enhance the learning of ESL in the context of KPK.

The development of culturally liable practices of ESL teaching is very important in the light of current findings, as it improves the ability to comprehend the English Language and its importance while keeping it intact with the cultural context of the learners. Multimedia and other resources have also been proven beneficial in displaying the diverse cultural experiences.

Promoting and providing training to ESL teachers for professional development is highly recommended and important. ESL teachers should also be equipped with plans and policies to deal with barriers that cultural factors prove to be in the way of ESL learning.

5.2. Future Implications

The current study highlights future directions and implications for the learning and teaching of ESL.

The study can help promote the culture of comparing and contrasting the learning of ESL practices with other contexts and factors. Personalizing ESL teaching methods in regard to the overall cultural context of the students is also one of the future implications of the current study.

The integration of culturally sensitive tools, such as digital and technologically advanced tools to test innovative solutions to the problem of cultural factors being a barrier, is also a likely implication of this study.

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